

The role of artificial intelligence in education

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Abstract: In this article, the concept of artificial intelligence, which occupies an important place in our daily lives, is developing to the extent that it can solve our existing problems, is widely used in all areas of the information society, especially in the field of education, this article gives information about their importance in learning and teaching.

Key words: artificial intelligence, field, activity, robots, history, financial field, transport field, learning and teaching , informations, tutoring, personalized, Artificial intelligence's benefits and disadvantages.

Nowadays, artificial intelligence is developing all over the world, and the main advantage of this is that it can find solutions to some problems in our life like the human mind, and it is gaining an important role not only in daily life, but also in the field of education. At this moment, we have a question: what is artificial intelligence? what role does it play in our education system?

The concept of artificial intelligence has many meanings. In its most common meaning, artificial intelligence is the science or field of creating machines that can imitate human mental activity. When we say artificial intelligence, we cannot know only computers or devices, but internet search engines: Google search, recommendation systems: you tube, Netflix, language understanding systems: google assistant, Alexa, and self self-driving cars: Waymo, and robots are examples. When we say robots, we mean assistants that can talk like humans, do things that humans do, but that's a broader concept. As far as the history of artificial intelligence is concerned, 1990 was a great year when a computer called Deep Blue became the first computer to beat chess master and all-time champion Garry Kasparov. Artificial intelligence is so advanced that residents of the Chinese city of Incheon no longer need bank cards, because the function of the card is performed by artificial intelligence by recognizing the facial features of a person. Also, artificial intelligence consists of algorithms and programs. In short, artificial intelligence is technology that can think like a human. Although the term artificial intelligence was introduced to science in 1956 by John McCarthy, the first research on it was carried

out by Alan Turing. Also, artificial intelligence is being used in any sphere of society. An example of this is the financial field. In the financial field. It is used to identify financial risk, manage bank credit situations, and detect financial fraud. And in the field of transport, we can analyze the traffic videos, which means that the camera will work on it and prevent the possible danger. And one of the most necessary fields is the medical field, because in this field, robots have been produced, they are quick assistants that do some things that doctors do, for example, to get information about the condition of patients, to deliver them the necessary pills. In a general sense, artificial intelligence refers to all the technologies that we need to get information, to find solutions to some of our problems, to perform some of the activities that we need. And now information is given about the role of artificial intelligence in learning and teaching, one of the important areas in our life.

Although AI is still in its infancy in the field of education, it can later serve as a platform for students and learners to meet their educational needs. Education by being able to analyze large amounts of data, provide students and learners with the information they need quickly, offer effective educational programs to teachers, and help with self-study, can occupy an important place in the field. Benefits of AI for learning include:

1. **Personalized Curriculum:** AI offers education and training programs personalized to the interests, age, and outlook of preschoolers to students based on their needs. It increases their interest in learning.

2. **Self-study and developed tutoring:** Currently there are educational programs based on tutoring. It's true that if they can't give students as much advice as their tutors, they'll get to that point in the near future. For example, AI can give students who want to self-study without a tutor several directions to find the necessary resources, information, which means that they can create self-study program plans. Because some families may not have enough money to go to a tutor, that's why AL is useful and economical.

3. **Access to information at any time:** Another benefit of AL for readers and students is that they can get their information quickly whenever they want. An example of this is CHATGPT produced in 2022. They get the information they need quickly through CHATGPT and similar platforms, which is the best helper not only during class but also in extracurricular activities.

Artificial intelligence has its place not only in learning, but also in teaching:

1. **Assessment Process:** When asked, any teacher will say that the most time-consuming issue is assessment, as they may not have time to assess all students

throughout the lesson. And AL has the ability to facilitate and speed up this process for them.

2. Offer Effective Lessons: Every teacher has their own way of teaching and they use that method while teaching, but that way can be boring for some students. At this point, they lose interest in learning, and AL can offer teachers effective and interactive lessons. It can also help teachers improve their teaching methods and increase students' interest in learning.

3. AL in the exam: at the time of taking the exam from the students, it is possible to observe and determine with the help of electronic cameras that they are taking the exam correctly and without using any information, that is, relying on their own knowledge.

Along with the benefits of artificial intelligence in the field of education, it is also necessary to mention the disadvantages. When talking about the harmful aspects of AL, it is necessary to pay attention to the opinions of the founders of famous companies and websites. In particular, Mark Sucerberg, the founder of Facebook, says that "The development of technologies will show its positive aspects in the next 10 years." But the founder of SpaceX, Elon Musk, and the founder of Microsoft, Bill Gates, said that "The ability of robots to perform all tasks will have a negative impact on work and may cause several risks for us."

AI actually has its benefits as well as its drawbacks.. This can also be seen in the field of Education. Negative Effects of AL in Teaching: AL has always supported technology while rejecting traditional teaching. This can reduce the role of teachers in the field of education. Because, in modern society, students rely not on the knowledge of their teachers, but on technologies and artificial assistants. Disadvantages of AL in Learning: Of course, every student or learner needs to use AL in some difficult situations or when information and feedback are lacking. But you don't need to rely on it constantly. Nowadays, especially in writing skills, students rely on the help of platforms like CHATGPT and Google research rather than their own knowledge. This leads to a decrease in the level of literacy among them.

In conclusion, the role of Artificial Intelligence in education has both positive and negative aspects. It should be used only when it is necessary, or when it can benefit a person. In any other situation, his own intelligence should be in the first place for him. As mobile as artificial intelligence is, the human mind and thinking is even more powerful. Because this intellect is created by man based on his mental literacy.

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